

ON CHLORALAMIDES. THE REACTION OF PHOSPHORUS PENTACHLORIDE ON CHLORAL-CHLOROSALICYL- AMIDES AND THEIR METHYL ETHERS, AND THE REACTIVITY OF THE CHLORINE ATOM.

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The methyl ethers of chloral-chlorosalicylamides have been reacted with phosphorus pentachloride and the corresponding α -chloro compounds have been isolated.

The α -chlorine atom is very reactive and has been found to react with water, alcohols, amines, phenols and organic acids, yielding related derivatives.

Feist, Nissen and Städler (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 1173) found that the α -hydroxyl group in chloral-aminonia derivatives, $R'CO \cdot NH \cdot CH(OH) \cdot CCl_3$, is replaced by halogen by phosphorus halides. Chloral-chlorosalicylamides (*Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1346) gave no definite products owing to the presence of free phenolic group (*cf.* Anschütz, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 221; Cohen, "Organic Chemistry," 1931, Vol. I, p. 408). When this group is methylated definite α -chloro compounds, *e.g.*,

are isolated.

The α -chlorine atom is far more reactive than the α -hydroxyl group (*cf.* Hirwe and Rana, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1938, 7, iii, 174). It reacts with water regenerating the parent compound and reacts with alcohols, amines, phenols and organic acids yielding the corresponding derivatives. The reaction is easier and quicker with alcohols and bases than with phenols and acids.

The reactivity of α -chloro compounds seems to depend on the position and number of the chlorine atoms in the nucleus. They are slowly converted by atmospheric moisture into the original compounds. Thus, they could be only crystallised from dry, inert solvents and have to be preserved in a desiccator.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

α -Chlorochloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide.—A mixture of chloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide (7 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (5 g.) was

heated on a water-bath, out of contact with atmospheric moisture, until the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased and a clear yellow liquid resulted. When it was poured on to crushed ice after cooling, a sticky mass separated which gradually solidified after being triturated with ice-water. The solid was filtered off, washed with ice-water and dried in a desiccator. The compound, which is soluble in acetone, benzene and toluene, crystallised from dry acetone in colourless plates, m.p. 144-45°, yield 7 g. It gave no colouration with ferric chloride. It developed slightly violet tinge on long standing even when protected from moist air. (Found : N, 4'09 ; Cl, 50'64. $C_{10}H_8O_2NCl_3$ requires N, 3'98 ; Cl, 50'51 per cent).

α-Methoxychloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide.— *α*-Chlorochloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide (2 g.) was heated under reflux, protected from moisture, with methanol (20 c.c.) on a water-bath for about 2 hours, when it completely went into solution. On cooling, white cubes separated which had m.p. 131-32° after recrystallisation from methanol. It gave no colouration with ferric chloride and showed no depression of m.p. on admixture with a pure sample of *α*-methoxychloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide (Hirwe and Rana, *loc. cit.*). (Found : Cl, 40'69. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3NCl_4$ requires Cl, 40'93 per cent).

α-Ethoxychloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide was prepared as described above, absolute alcohol replacing methanol. The compound crystallised from alcohol in white prisms, m.p. 137-38° and gave no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found : Cl, 39'14. $C_{12}H_{13}O_3NCl_4$ requires Cl, 39'33 per cent).

α-Anilinochloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide.— *α*-Chlorochloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide (2 g.) was heated with aniline (5 c.c.) on a water-bath for 2 hours. After standing overnight at room temperature the mixture gave a pasty mass on pouring into water, which solidified when triturated with dilute hydrochloric acid. The compound crystallised from alcohol in white silky needles, m.p. 152-53°. It gave no ferric chloride reaction. (Found : N, 6'74 ; Cl, 34'84. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2Cl_4$ requires N, 6'86 ; Cl, 34'80 per cent).

o-, *m*- and *p*-*Toluidinochloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamides* were similarly prepared. These compounds gave no colouration with ferric chloride.

The *o*-toluidino derivative crystallised from alcohol in colourless, thick needles which slightly darkened on long exposure, m.p. 148-49°. (Found : Cl, 33'57. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 33'65 per cent).

The *m*-toluidino derivative crystallised from alcohol in colourless flakes which also darkened on exposure, m.p. 153-54°. (Found : Cl, 33'98. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 33'65 per cent).

The *p*-toluidino derivative crystallised in white needles from warm alcohol in which it is difficultly soluble, m. p. 169-70°. (Found : Cl, 33'67. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2Cl_4$ requires Cl, 33'65 per cent).

α-Phenoxychloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide.—*α*-Chlorochloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide (2 g.) was heated with phenol (2 g.) on a water-bath for 4 hours protected from moisture. On pouring the clear mixture into ice-water an oil separated which was washed several times with water. It immediately solidified in contact with alcohol. The compound crystallised from alcohol in white, shining prisms, m.p. 194-95°. It gave no ferric reaction. (Found : Cl, 34'82. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3NCl_4$ requires Cl, 34'72 per cent).

α-Benzoyloxychloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide.—A finely powdered mixture of *α*-chlorochloral-5-chloro-2-methoxybenzamide (2 g.) and benzoic acid (2 g.), suspended in dry benzene, was heated under reflux, protected from moisture, on a water-bath for 2 hours. On concentrating the solution, a pasty mass was obtained which was treated with hot water to remove the excess of benzoic acid. The paste ultimately solidified on keeping in contact with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution for a few hours. The solid crystallised from alcohol in white small plates, m.p. 133-35° and gave no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found : Cl, 32'70. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4NCl_4$ requires Cl, 32'49 per cent).

α-Chlorochloral-3 : 5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide.—Chloral-3 : 5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide gave the substance on treatment with phosphorus pentachloride in the usual manner. The compound, which is soluble in acetone, benzene and toluene, crystallised from dry benzene in colourless, rectangular plates, m.p. 89-91°, yield 7'5 g. There was a fall of about 3-4° in the m.p. after about a week. It darkened on exposure and gave no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found : Cl, 55'09. $C_{10}H_7O_2NCl_6$ requires Cl, 55'18 per cent).

α-Methoxychloral-3 : 5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide.—*α*-Chlorochloral-3 : 5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide and methanol gave the substance when reacted in the usual manner. The compound crystallised from methanol in white prisms, m.p. 102-3°, and gave no colouration with ferric chloride. It showed no depression on admixture with an authentic specimen of *α*-methoxychloral-3 : 5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide (Hirwe and Rana, *loc. cit.*). (Found : Cl, 46'30. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3NCl_5$ requires Cl, 46'52 per cent).

α-Anilinochloral-3 : 5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide, prepared as above, crystallised from alcohol in white, shining needles, m.p. 147-48°, and gave

no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found : Cl, 40·24. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_2Cl_5$ requires Cl, 40·12 per cent).

o-*o*-, *m*- and *p*-Toluidinochloral-3 : 5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamides.—
The *o*-toluidino derivative, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from alcohol in colourless, shining needles, m.p. 153-54°. (Found : Cl, 38·67. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N_2Cl_5$ requires Cl, 38·88 per cent).

The *m*-toluidino derivative crystallised from alcohol in colourless, shining needles which, however, slightly darkened on long exposure, m.p. 146-47°. (Found : Cl, 38·75. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N_2Cl_5$ requires Cl, 38·88 per cent).

The *p*-toluidino derivative crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 145-46°. (Found : Cl, 38·57. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N_2Cl_5$ requires Cl, 38·88 per cent). No ferric reaction was given by any of these compounds.

a-Phenoxychloral-3 : 5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide was prepared from *a*-chlorochloral-3 : 5-dichloro-2-methoxybenzamide (2 g.) and phenol (2 g.). The product crystallised from alcohol in white minute needles, m.p. 125-26°, and gave no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found : Cl, 40·19. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3NCl_5$ requires Cl, 40·02 per cent).

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